

CONTROLS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF PUBLIC PROCUREMENT

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Abstract: The article describes the need to control public procurement and the mechanism of its implementation.

Key words: control of public procurement, authorities in the field of procurement, regulatory bodies

The main goals of state regulation of the public procurement sector are to achieve the strategic goals and objectives of the state; ensuring the needs of state customers for goods (works, services); Implementation of the Investment Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other state programs; performing functions of the state to solve social tasks; consists of creating a favorable environment for public procurement entities to provide public services, as well as fight against corruption and other violations of the law in the implementation of public procurement.

In the implementation of public procurement, socio-economic policy priorities, including the creation of high-tech and innovative productions, and the maintenance of a favorable environmental situation, are taken into account.

If at least three domestic producers, along with foreign suppliers, participate in the state procurement of goods (works, services), unless otherwise stipulated in the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan, according to the decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan domestic producers may be given incentives and preferences used in the evaluation of bids.

State procurement of goods (works, services) necessary to meet the needs

of the Republic of Uzbekistan can be carried out in cooperation with foreign countries. The procedure for the implementation of such state procurement is determined by the international agreement of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan ensures the formation and implementation of state policy in the field of public procurement. In addition, in the field of public procurement, the budget system takes measures for the rational use of budget funds, improvement of the types of procurement procedures and expansion of their application, as well as ensuring wide participation of business entities.

In addition, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan coordinates work on control over the activities of state customers in the field of public procurement; determines the methods and criteria for evaluating and comparing bids of participants in procurement procedures, as well as the procedure for organizing their conduct; determines the procedure for the selection of the best offers by the participants of procurement procedures and the submission of offers in electronic form for participation in the tender; approves the composition of the commission for considering complaints in the field of public procurement.

The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the competent body in the field of public procurement. Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- carries out state regulation and state policy in the field of public procurement;
- takes measures to increase the efficiency and openness of the implementation and development of programs for the development of the system of organizing and conducting public procurement, including the electronic system;
- defines the operators of the public procurement electronic system and the

procedure for their activities related to the organization and implementation of public procurement, as well as the procedure for the operation of the special information portal;

- specifies requirements for the electronic system of public procurement;
- develops the procedure for applying the method of evaluation of the most economically advantageous offer (non-price evaluation criteria);
- determines the order and volume of posting, disclosure and use of information on public procurement, as well as additional requirements for publication depending on the goods (work, service) and the method of public procurement;
- approves the model forms of announcements on conducting procurement procedures, procurement documents;
- Develops and approves the procedure for forming a single register of dishonest performers;
- Determines the procedure for maintaining a single register of contracts;
- provides monitoring and control over the implementation of regulatory legal documents in the field of public procurement;
- requests information from public procurement subjects, collects, analyzes them and prepares reports;
- develops proposals for the introduction of a certification system for procurement and anti-corruption standards in the field of public procurement and submits them to the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan for consideration.

Monitoring in the field of public procurement is a monitoring system that is implemented on a permanent basis through the means of collecting, summarizing, systematizing and evaluating information about the conduct of public procurement to ensure compliance with the legislation on public procurement, the implementation of the goals, principles and limitations of public procurement

established by the Law. will consist of

Control in the field of public procurement consists of a system of measures aimed at preventing, identifying and putting an end to violations of legal requirements in this field.

Inspections carried out by comparison and analysis of statistical and other information in accordance with the procedure established by law are the main form of control over the compliance of state bodies with the laws on public procurement. Monitoring and control in the field of public procurement is carried out by the relevant competent state bodies.

During the organization and implementation of public procurement, it is not allowed to carry out inspections that are not provided for by law and to require reporting forms.

State control over the correct application of the law and other regulatory legal documents in the field of public procurement is carried out by the following within the scope of their powers:

- Accounts Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Committee to fight against monopoly of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The Accounts Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan conducts an audit of public purchases made by state customers and presents the audit results in the annual report to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as places them on open information sources.

State control over the correct application of the Law "On State Procurement" and other legislative documents in the field of state procurement is carried out in accordance with the legislation by other competent state bodies within their powers.

In our country, the legal basis for public control over procurement procedures has been created. Public control over procurement procedures is carried out in order to support the development and improvement of public procurement, to prevent and identify violations of the legislative requirements on public procurement, and to inform state customers and authorized state bodies about detected violations.

Public control over procurement procedures is carried out by implementing the principles of openness and transparency.

Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan, self-government bodies of citizens, as well as non-governmental non-profit organizations and mass media registered in accordance with the procedure established by law, have the right to exercise public control over compliance with the legislation on state procurement.

Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan exercising public control, self-government bodies of citizens, as well as non-governmental non-profit organizations and mass media registered in accordance with the law: to prepare proposals for improving the legislation on public procurement ; to send requests to state customers to provide information on the implementation of procurement procedures and the progress of contract execution; to carry out independent monitoring of procurement procedures and evaluation of the efficiency of public procurement, including the assessment of their compliance with the requirements of the Law "On Public Procurement"; they have the right to apply to state bodies with the initiative of carrying out inspection activities.

Also, public representatives have the authority to apply to law enforcement agencies or to apply to the court in accordance with the law in cases where violations are detected in the actions (inaction) of the state customer, operator of the state electronic procurement system, authorized body, procurement commissions and their members.

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